

E-Waste Management- An Overview

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ABSTRACT

Electronic Waste or Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) are the ones which are loosely rejected, out-dated, damaged electrical or electronic equipments which are dangerous to the environment and affect the health of the human beings. Therefore Electronic Waste Management is very essential in present day life. These waste electrical equipments can be reused and recycled. Various Administrations, bodies, and governments of countries have implemented and established strategies for Electronic Waste Management to cope up with the threat of Electronic Waste to the environmental setting and health of humans. Electronic Waste includes non-ferrous and costly metals extracted from the equipments which are out-dated. This paper focuses on E-waste composition, Indian E-waste scenarios, dangerous materials found in the Electronic Waste, Best Practices, reusing, and regaining methods followed in order to safeguard the environment. Electronic waste is a major threat faced by many countries so the government focuses on reducing and eliminating the E-waste by adopting various techniques and best practices to safeguard the health of the humans and environment.

Keywords: Electronic Waste, Reuse, Dangerous materials, Electrical equipments, Environment

I. INTRODUCTION:

Electronic Waste is electronic goods that are undesirable, not working or at the completion of their “useful life.” Electronic Waste comprises precious and recoverable metals which can be reused and recycled.

Electronic Waste are dangerous to human beings and atmosphere as it contains various harmful chemicals which end up soil, water and air if discarded without handling properly. Improper handling and discarding of electronic equipments affects the human life and the ecosystem. Therefore E-waste management has become very crucial and being realised. Discarding of the electronic items without reuse also leads to environment pollution to the society. Extent of E-waste has enlarged due to technological advancements were the equipments become obsolete soon which will be replaced by new machines.

Fig 1: E-waste Management

Electronic Waste Management plays very crucial role by using every techniques and strategies to cope up with the Electronic Waste and safeguard the atmosphere as a whole. Therefore many organisations and government of various countries have accepted and established strategies for Electronic Waste Management to protect the human health and the overall environment. Countries can go for reusing and recycling of the electronic items which becomes obsolete after certain period.

2. OBJECTIVES:

- To study the Opportunities and Challenges of Electronic Waste Management.
- To highlight on the Initiatives and Best Practices in Electronic Waste Management.
- To analyze hazardous materials in Electronic Waste.
- To focus on the Electronic Waste Management reusing and recovery processes.

3. METHODOLOGY:

The study is carried out using the secondary source of information. The data is being collected through various sites and journal articles.

4. LIMITATIONS:

- The study is restricted only to the secondary information.
- In depth study on E-waste Management was not possible.

5. OPPORTUNITIES OF ELECTRONIC WASTE MANAGEMENT:

Electronic waste is generated when the electrical equipment become old and out-dated. These electronic equipments get replaced with newer models due to the rapid growth of technology. Computers, printers, washing machine, air conditioners, refrigerators, cellular phones, calculators, scanners etc. are illustrations of Electronic Waste when they are not fit for use. The Ministry of Environment, forest and the changes in Climate had brought the Electronic Waste Management rules in the year 2016 to decrease production of Electronic waste and to increase reusing. E-waste management which is increasing in nature is rich in various metals which is collected and used in the process of production. Large number of people is provided with the job opportunities. Government introduced Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) where manufacturers are liable in collecting 30% to 70% of the Electronic waste they produce. The combination of the informal sector into the transparent recycling system is very essential for welfare of the environment and the human health. The informal sectors should be guided in order to authorise and take the initiative of collecting system where manual dismantling is being replaced by the latest technology which yields high revenue. Electronic waste is a rich source of metals which is recovered and used for production to both individuals and enterprises to earn income. In 2018, Government amended the Electronic Waste Management Rules, 2016 to put into use the Electronic Waste Management which is environmental friendly. The targets of collection have been changed and the monitoring of Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) would ensure effective management of Electronic Waste.

6. INITIATIVES AND BEST PRACTICES IN E-WASTE MANAGEMENT:

Consumers are the essential element to manage the Electronic waste in a better way. . Advancement in Information Technology and Communication sectors has increased demand in using the electronic equipments. Quicker development in electronic product forces the consumers to go for new products and discard the old outdated products. As the problems of E-waste increases it focuses on various initiatives undertaken to manage the E-waste efficiently. The various initiatives and best practices in E-waste management are as follows.

- **Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR):**

This focuses on the responsibility i.e., financial and physical put on the producers for the treatment of disposal of products which have become obsolete. This helps to prevent waste and protect the environment as the E-waste are collected by the producers and segregated as it could be recycled and could be used in the production of new products.

- **Design for Environment (DfE):**

This initiative concentrates on the protecting the environment while handling the electronic items that have become obsolete. Due care has to be taken during production and recycling of the products where use of hazardous and toxic material should be avoided. Designers can take up decisions of using such materials which reduces the environmental impact, resulting in less greenhouse gas emissions and using the natural resources efficiently.

- **Reduce, Reuse, Recycle (3Rs):**

These are the essential components of protecting the environment and reducing E-waste. Whenever any production and consumption is done, it should be seen that whether it is required and essential. Unnecessary materials should not be purchased and there should be reduction in the consumption which cuts down the waste. Reusing means repeated use of the materials and parts of the material which has usable aspects. Recycling is making use of the waste items and bringing new items. These are the three ways which minimises the waste accumulation in the society.

- **Increased reuse and recycling rates:**

People should be made aware about the problems face due to E-waste. They should be encouraged to increase reuse and recycle of the outdated equipments.

- **Adopting sustainable consumer habits:**

Consumers should develop the habits of protecting the environment by reducing and managing the waste. It helps to achieve sustainable environment where the pollution is reduced and safeguarding the health of the people.

7. CHALLENGES OF ELECTRONIC WASTE MANAGEMENT:

Electronic waste is very hazardous to life if it is not dismantled and processed in a systematic manner as it is made up of toxic substances. India has taken fifth place in the generation of Electronic waste producing about 1.7 lakhs metric tonnes in a year.

Fig 2: Challenges of Electronic Waste Management

- Electronic waste should be properly processed and recycled as it affects the life of humans, animals and the environment as a whole.
- Involvement of children in electronic waste management activities is biggest challenge as the children of age group 10-14 are involved in various E-waste activities such as collection, segregation and distribution without adequate protection and safety in various yards and recycling workshops. Therefore effective legislation should be bought to prevent child labour into E-waste market.
- Pollution Control Committees (PCC) has not uploaded the basic guidelines of Electronic waste in the websites. If the information of collectors and reusers are not mentioned in the website, the citizens and Institutional generators of Electronic waste find it difficult to fulfil their responsibility.
- Huge difference between the reusing facilities and quantity of Electronic waste generated. There is lack of availability of facilities.
- No incentive schemes are provided for the producers involved in the handling of Electronic waste which do not motivate them to handle the E-waste effectively.
- People are not aware on the disposal of the electronic and electrical equipments as they are not educated on how to handle the Electronic waste after its useful life. Only few people are aware on the problems that arise on their health and environment due to the improper handling of Electronic waste.
- There is no clarity on the description of roles and responsibilities that has to be played by the stakeholders and institutions involved in Electronic waste management.

8. HAZARDOUS MATERIALS IN ELECTRONIC WASTE:

Electronic equipments get replaced quickly with new models due to the advancement of technology. It consists of various metals and toxic substances harmful for health. It affects the human beings, animals and the environment as a whole. E-waste consists of various components such as metals, plastics, cathode ray tubes (CRTs), printed circuit boards, cables, and so on. Certain valuable metals are recovered from E-waste if it is processed systematically and scientifically. Valuable metals are copper, silver, gold and platinum are recovered and use in the production process of the newer products. The presence of various toxic substances such as liquid crystal, lithium, mercury, nickel, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), selenium, arsenic, barium, brominated flame retardants, cadmium, chrome, cobalt, copper, and lead, makes it very dangerous, if it is not disposed and handled in a proper manner. The existence of heavy metals and toxic substances such as mercury, lead, beryllium, and cadmium give threat to the environment even though their fraction is small. The fraction including iron, copper, aluminum, gold, and other metals in e-waste is over 60%, while plastics account for about 30% and the hazardous pollutants comprise only about 2.70%. Lead is used in larger quantities in electronic devices resulting in various health hazards due to environmental

contamination and pollution. Children are prone to lead poisoning more as compared to adults because they absorb more lead from the environment and their nervous system and blood get affected. It also results in skin damage, headaches, vertigo, nausea, chronic gastritis, and gastric and duodenal ulcers.

9. E-WASTE RECYCLING PROCESS:

Recycling of electronic items is a challenging activity. The production of the electronic items is done using different metals. The recycling process is carried out through various steps:

Step 1: Collection and Transportation:

In this step, the recyclers place bins and boxes in specific areas for people to dump their electronic waste in it. Once the bin is filled it is collected and transported to the recycling plants.

Step 2: Shredding and Sorting:

Shredding involves breaking the E-waste materials into smaller pieces. This is usually done with hands which is labour intensive as the waste items are separated. Then the materials are classified into core materials and components. Later they are organised into different groups.

Fig 3: E-Waste Management process.

Step 3: Dust Removal:

During this stage, the tiny waste particles get smoothly spread by shaking process on a conveyor belt. Smoothly spread E-waste pieces then gets broken down even further. So the dust gets extracted and discarded without affecting the environment.

Step 4: Magnetic Separation:

During this stage a strong magnet helps to separate steel and iron from other waste particles. However, some other processes may be needed to separate items which are mostly plastics.

Step 5: Water Separation:

Once the water separation is done, it becomes important to separate the glass from the plastics.

Step 6: purification of waste stream:

The next step is to find out and remove leftover metals from plastics to purify the waste stream further.

Step 7: Preparing recycled materials for sale:

The final stage in the recycling process is to sell the recycled materials. It can be sold as raw materials to produce new electronic items.

10. FINDINGS

- As compared to the various countries on the Environmental Performance Index 2018, India ranks 177 amongst 180 countries.
- Among the top Electronic waste producing countries in the world, India is ranked fifth and the annual recycling is less than 2% of the total Electronic waste.
- India generates more than two million tons of Electronic waste annually, and also imports huge amounts of Electronic waste from other countries.
- Seelampur in Delhi is largest Electronic waste disassembling Centre in India. Adults as well as children spend 8–10 hours daily removing precious metals from various devices.
- Children around 10-14 years are involved in the activities carried on at recycling plants which has given scope for child labour.
- There exists huge difference in quantity of Electronic waste produced and the recycling facilities available.

11. SUGGESTIONS:

1. Awareness should be provided to the industrialist and the general public on the different way of handling and disposing E-waste.
2. Legislation should be passed for the abolition of child labour where children from age 10-14 years should not be given jobs.
3. Adequate recycling facilities should be arranged so as to match with the amount of E-waste generation.
4. Incentive schemes should be provided for the producers engaged in the proper handling of Electronic waste which motivates them.

12. CONCLUSION:

E-waste is major environmental problems of the world. Lack of awareness is the main reason for the increase in the E-waste which has become a serious issue in the country. The greatest challenge faced by the governments of many developing countries such as India is E-waste Management. The competent authorities in developing countries need to establish devices and machines for handling and treatment of E-waste in a safe and sustainable manner. Mobile phone manufacturer Nokia is one of the very few companies which have made serious effort in E-waste Management since 2008. Violation of E-waste rules by some big companies led to the suspension of import license. These actions and measures have led to a great impact on effective implementation of E-waste management in India.

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